

Upcycling sawmill residues to value-added fibre products

Through smart utilisation of wood side streams and post-consumer wood, material efficiency of wood improves. Technical fibre products for different purposes enhance profitability of wood-based products. Application fields can vary from animal feed, the food industry to filter aids, fillers or functional fibres in biocomposites. Various technological material solutions exist and are ready to be exploited in optimal processing of even the smallest residues. Post-consumer wood is only suitable for technical applications and not for food and feed. For the wood fibre processors, animal feed is a significant and growing market. Wood fibres are also used as extract cellulose mainly as a filter aids for the food industry.

Image: Holzmühle Westerkamp

Why is it a good practice?

- ▶ 100% recycled wood provides the highest level of recycling of today
- ▶ Advanced waste management facilitates postconsumer wood to be used as wood fibres for technical and added value applications
- ▶ Wood- and food fibres are a sustainable solution for many sectors
- ▶ Technical wood fibres provide functional use for side streams
- ▶ The public acceptance for post-consumer wood fibres is enhanced
- ▶ The resource efficiency of wood is raised by cascading activities

Regional coverage and transferability

The leading companies selling fibres for a broad range of applications are identified today in Central and Northern Europe but more and more small companies across Europe are also selling fibres for different application and valorisation areas.

The technology is transferable to dominant wood processing countries and regions with a focus to North and Central Europe.

